

D6.2. Public Launch of the Project, and Communication and Public Engagement Plans

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Executive summary

The present document details the GuestXR project communication and public engagement activities, aiming at reaching as many relevant actors as possible to inform them on the activities and results derived from the project. EUT is responsible for designing and implementing it, but all consortium partners will be involved in it.

The channels and platforms considered in the communication and public engagement plan are: social media channels, official website, materials to be distributed in key events, media relations to specialized media outlets, the creation of a community of interest, and the organisation of engagement activities, among others.

This deliverable details the target groups, key messages addressed to each main group of stakeholders, the activities planned, requirements and the process of reporting communication activities.

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List of abbreviations

AR	Augmented reality
D	Deliverable
EU	European Union
ML	Machine Learning
MR	Mixed reality
RL	Reinforcing Learning
T	Task
VCI	Visual Corporate Identity
VR	Virtual Reality

1. Introduction

GuestXR is a three-year project aiming to create an immersive online social space through extended reality, where the focus is on the existence of a machine learning agent, called “The Guest”, facilitating interaction between participants to help them achieve their intended goals.

EUT is the leader of **WP6 Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation** and **Task 6.1. Dissemination and communication**, which is related to the present deliverable. EUT is responsible for defining the project's Communication and Engagement Plan.

The GuestXR Communication and Engagement Plan has the objective to raise awareness on the project's main goals and activities, communicate the project results and activities to as many relevant actors as possible, and support all project activities and train the next generation of researchers and industry professionals.

This document compiles the communication activities, including the creation and maintenance of the project's website, social media channels and posts, the creation of promotional materials, press releases, newsletters, and the organization of engagement events.

This deliverable also includes the communication objectives, key messages, target audiences and timing of activities. Key performance indicators (KPIs) for each communication activity are defined and reported, ensuring the traceability of the activities that are not listed under particular deliverables or milestones.

2. Communication and public engagement plan

The main goals of the GuestXR project communication and public engagement strategy are:

- Increase the global visibility of GuestXR and its outcomes in Europe and beyond.
- Develop novel communication and engagement activities to facilitate knowledge transfer to a broad range of stakeholders including specialised and non-specialised audiences.
- Raise awareness on the project, its funding, and its impact on the European VR industry.

It is worth noting that in order to protect the commercial interests of the partners, the publication of the materials will be selective, except for the submission of contractually required reports and information to the Commission. In this case, partners decide which part of the project's information is to be protected by copyright or trade secrets and which part of the information is suitable for disseminating widely.

All the actions will consider EC recommendations explained in the Participant Portal H2020 Online Manual section on project communication¹.

2.1 Target of communication and dissemination

An initial analysis of the dissemination and communication target audiences has been done. Six stakeholder groups have been identified as the target audiences of the communication and

¹ http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding_guide/grants/grantmanagement/dissemination-of-results_en.htm

public engagement activities, including: academia, industry, end-users / customers, policymakers, the user group, and the society at large. Detailed information is presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1: GuestXR stakeholders' groups

The process of identifying the key persons and entities that embody this stakeholder consideration is in progress. **A list of target contacts for all communication and dissemination activities is under development.** For this specific purpose, an excel file to record the stakeholders identified (containing just the name of the organization, country, and activity and without including personal information details) is stored in the GuestXR internal collaborative platform.

2.2 Channels

For communication and dissemination activities, the GuestXR project will use a wide range of channels and actions, ranging from social media activity, media relations, and promotional materials to the organization of stakeholder engagement events.

Besides the aforementioned project channels, all partners will make use of their own channels (websites, presence on Social Media, and corporate newsletters/publications) to disseminate news about GuestXR and reach a broader audience.

Figure 2: Communication channels and activities

2.3 Key messages for communication

Several key messages have been defined, which will be evolved throughout the project and tailored according to the target audience, including both specialists and non-specialists, in order to enhance the reach of the project research, actions and results.

General GuestXR messages include:

- GuestXR will develop an immersive online social space based on extended reality through a Machine Learning agent called “The Guest”, which can facilitate interaction between participants to help them achieve their goals.
- “The Guest” can analyse and act upon the individual and social behaviour of the participants based on existing theoretical models from the point of view of neuroscience and social psychology.
- The GuestXR innovation addresses the lack of regulation in social interaction environments seeking to help avert conflicts and cyberbullying in digital interaction environments, making it easier for people with communication problems to get involved and detecting antisocial behaviour.
- The project is developed under the “Ethics by Design” approach, thus considering any potential ethical issues which may come up when using Artificial Intelligence such as respect for human autonomy, prevention of harm, fairness, and explicability.
- GuestXR Machine Learning agent solution is to be tested in social situations that may generate conflict, during interactions involving participants with communication problems, or in contexts that trigger debate, such as climate change.
- GuestXR is a project funded by the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme contributing to making use of Artificial Intelligence for improving social interaction.

The messages need to translate the **possibilities and strengths of the developments** within GuestXR. The communication messages will be **carefully designed and tailored to very each of the stakeholders**. All the communication contents will be **adapted to the different channels** used in GuestXR.

3. Communication and public engagement management

3.1 Acknowledgments

All communication materials produced in the project (website, promotional materials, etc.) and distributed in physical or electronic format (e.g. social media) will display the EU emblem and funding text provided below, in line with the EU regulations described in the Grant Agreement:

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101017884.

In addition, whenever possible results to include the following disclaimer:

[This result NAME] reflects only the author's view and the Agency / Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

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 Do you have any questions? Send us an e-mail and we will reply to you as soon as possible.
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Figure 3: Example of acknowledgment application in GuestXR website

3.2 Risks and mitigation measures

The risks faced in the completion of activities planned in WP6 and potential mitigation measures have been defined and are presented in Table 3. This table will be reviewed periodically to spot any new risks and determine if there is a need to put in place mitigation actions.

The exposure to a given risk is estimated using the risk matrix as following:

Impact \ Probability	1- Extremely unlikely	2- Likely	3- Extremely likely
1- Not critical	1	2	3
2- Significant	2	4	6
3- Fundamental to continuing operations	3	6	9

Risk score = Impact x Probability **Priority:** ■ High ■ Medium ■ Low

Figure 4: Risk management matrix

Table 1: GuestXR identified risks and mitigation measures

Risks	Probability / Impact	Mitigation measures
The audience has difficulty to understanding GuestXR technology	Medium / High	Usage of real examples, plain language, showcase and validate the technology through use cases and adapt the technology and language to different contexts as well as the audience's needs.
Communication is unsuccessful	Low / low	The regular monitorisation and evaluation of communication content. Constant proactivity with users to establish strong relationships. Sufficient resources are allocated for communication activities.

Not enough engagement on GuestXR communication channels	Medium / Medium	Creation of more content for the project website and social media that engages stakeholders, increase the frequency of publication on project channels.
Low project visibility	Low/Low	Develop an appealing website and communication materials. Organise joint activities with other initiatives and projects.
Harmful events for the reputation of GuestXR or there is an ethics breach	Medium / Medium	The need to establish strong ethics policies, conduct proactive communication through a multitude of channels and adopt strategies to increase users' perceptions of quality.

3.3 KPIs

Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) have been assigned to a number of communication activities planned in the project in order to assess their performance and impact by the end of the project. These are listed in Table 2.

Table 2: GuestXR Communication KPIs

Strategy	Indicator	Means of verification	Target by the end of the project
Website	Number of web visits	Matomo Analytics	>2.000 annually in avg.
	Number Pages Viewed		>2.000 annually in avg.
	Number page / session		>1.0
	Number users		>500 annually in avg.
	Avg. session time		>1.00 min
Social Media (Twitter)	Number of followers	Twitter Analytics	>200
	Number of tweets		>500 - <i>At least 2 per week</i>
	Number of impressions		>100K
	Number of mentions		>100
	Number of Retweets		>150
	Number of Likes		>100
Social Media (LinkedIn)	Number of followers	LinkedIn Analytics	>150
	Number of posts		>100
	Number of impressions		>15K
	Number of likes / reactions		>150
	Number of shares		>50
Social Media (YouTube)	Number of videos uploaded	YouTube Analytics	>25
	Number of visualisations		>2,000
Newsletter	Number of issues	Proof of publication and reporting in reports / project meetings	4 issues
	Number of subscribers		>200 (<i>at least 50 subscriptions per year</i>)
	Number of press releases		4 annually in average

Media relations	Number of articles in generalistic newspapers	Proof of publication and reporting in reports / project meetings	>20 articles
	Number of articles published in scientific outlets		10 articles
Promotional materials	Number of brochures	Proof of publication and reporting in reports / project meetings	1
	Brochures downloads		100 annual downloads
	Project presentation		1
	Number of infosheets		1
	Number of rollups		1
	Number of videos		>25

3.3.1 KPIs reporting

Progress until the end of the project will be reported in Deliverables 6.3 and well as in interim progress reports. To facilitate the reporting, an excel file has been prepared to record monthly the KPIs progress. The file, stored in Sharepoint Collaborative Platform includes the following tabs related to communication activities:

- **Web and social media:** to report progress on project and partners channels
- **Media Clipping:** for recording articles in generalist and specialised media outlets

4. Communication and public engagement tools

5.1 Project branding and templates

Eurecat, as the leader of Task 6.1. has developed GuestXR's Corporate Visual Identity, including the project's logo, a Power Point template, Word templates for project activities, and a visual identity standards guidebook, defining and outlining how to use identifying elements pertaining to GuestXR, including logos, colours, fonts, stationery, and graphic resources. GuestXR project branding has been deployed throughout project materials and communication channels, being an asset for the public launch of the project.

1. See deliverable D6.1 for more information on the elements designed.

Figure 7. Full-colour GuestXR logo

Figure 8. Slides of GuestXR PowerPoint presentation template

Figure 9. View of some pages of the deliverable template

5.2 Project website

According to the work plan, Eurecat has been responsible for designing and implementing the official GuestXR project website and launching it on M2 (February 2022). The registered URL is www.guestxr.eu.

The website is the anchor for all communication and dissemination activities related to the project and serves as a central point of entry for all public material, including the project’s basic information, activities, and events. The website will be continuously updated with news, links to other relevant sites, and details of published papers, conferences and exhibitions during the project and will remain active at least three years after the project’s finalisation.

The website platform follows the corporate visual identity of the project, and it gives access to the GuestXR social media channels (Twitter, LinkedIn, and YouTube).

Considering that different authors might update the site, a Content Management System (CMS) has been adopted, to easily and quickly publish the content. The website is optimised for browsing on tablets and smartphones, so the website has been developed using a responsive design approach.

4.1.1 Structure and new pages created

The initial structure of the website has evolved into new pages. From M1-M6, the GuestXR website has been updated with the publication of new content to include specific information about project materials, media impacts, audiovisual materials, etc.

Figure 10: Project website at M6

4.1.1.1 Project news

All the information related to project news or events organised and participated by the consortium is allocated in the section “News & Events”.

Figure 11. GuestXR website "news & events" page

4.1.1.2 Event pages

Specific pages are being created and updated with information for every important event involving GuestXR, with the objective of maximising the visits and reach on the website.

For the time being, two event pages have been created: “Frontiers in Virtual Reality – Online Seminar Series” and “Symposium – XR for the people”.

The first one recaps all the information about the series of online seminars organised in collaboration with Frontiers in Virtual Reality Journal, which is running from M5 to M7 of the project.

On this page, users can register for each online seminar they wish. They can also see the video recording and download the presentations afterwards.

Online Seminar Series – Striving for Social Harmony in XR

25th May – 6th July 2022

By now we are likely to have come across horror stories from 'the metaverse' about how it is easy to encounter abuse, racism, misogyny, an overall unpleasant experience. On the other hand, social virtual environments have been studied for many years, and there is evidence about how people behave in virtual meetings. GuestXR is carrying out research towards how to make immersive virtual meetings realise the goals of the participants. Normally virtual meetings have a purpose, even if that is entertainment, and GuestXR has the ambitious aim of intervening in such meetings to make them fit for their purpose.

In this seminar series, partners from the GuestXR project will speak about their early work on these issues, covering a review of virtual meetings ('collaborative virtual environments'), the utility of agent based models for social modeling, what we can learn from the neuroscience of interpersonal interaction, the role of deep learning for virtual humans, and reflections on the ethical aspects.

Figure 12. View of "Frontiers in Virtual Reality - Online Seminar Series" page

The page "Symposium – XR for the people" includes information about an event hosted by the Advanced Reality Lab of the Reichman University. The symposium was participated by partners from the UB and UM.

Symposium: XR for the people

Science, technology, applications, and implications

Date: June 13th, 2022

Time: 12:30h – 19:00h GMT+3

Venue: Reichman University, Chais Auditorium (CL05), Arazi-Ofer building

Address: HaUniversita 8 8, Herzliya, 4610101, Israel

Figure 13: View of "XR for the people" symposium page

4.1.1.3 Media impact

This page was created around M5 (May 2020) when the first press release was produced and sent to partners' media contacts. This section gives access to relevant articles featuring GuestXR published in digital media at a local, national, and international level, as well as the press releases available. The section "Media impacts" will be continuously updated with more articles related to the project.

Resources

GuestXR in the news

See below a selection of articles featuring GuestXR:

May 17, 2022 | *Intelligence Artificielle*

[Machine learning : améliorer la gestion des conflits dans le metaverse \(French\)](#)

May 16, 2022 | *Tech Tribune*

[Un outil d'apprentissage automatique améliore la gestion des conflits dans le métaverse \(French\)](#)

May 16, 2022 | *Innovation Origins*

[Machine learning tool improves conflict management in the metaverse](#)

May 12, 2022 | *VIA Empresa*

[El proyecto GuestXR gestionará conflictos y situaciones de ciberacoso \(Spanish\)](#)

May 11, 2022 | *La Vanguardia*

[Sistema de aprendizaje automático ayudará a gestionar conflictos y ciberacoso \(Spanish\)](#)

Figure 14. View of "Media impacts" page

4.1.1.4 Project materials

This section was created around M5 (May 2022) once the project's promotional materials were validated and ready to be shared through all the communication channels. Promotional materials include a general presentation, an infosheet, a rollup, and a trifold.

This page will also include the different presentations and posters presented by partners in exhibitions, congresses, international conferences, and other key events.

Resources

Project materials

See below all dissemination materials available about the project, including, brochures, infosheets, rollups and a general presentation.

GuestXR – Infosheet 1 file(s) 252.17 KB	DOWNLOAD		
GuestXR – Trifold 1 file(s) 335.79 KB	DOWNLOAD		

Figure 15. View of the "Project materials" page

4.1.1.5 Audiovisual materials

This section was created in May 2022 (M5) to include all the videos related to GuestXR project that were published on the YouTube account. At M6 it includes five videos, which include an example of the application of GuestXR technology, video recordings of the webinars from “Striving for Social Harmony in XR”, as well as video recordings of scientific presentations done within consortium meetings.

The page will be constantly updated as soon as new project’s videos will be produced.

Resources

GuestXR videos

In this page you will be able to find all the videos related to GuestXR project published in our [YouTube channel](#)

Figure 16. View of the "Audiovisual materials" page

4.1.2 Analytics

GuestXR website has installed Matomo in the platform’s back end to monitor all the traffic and obtain, periodically, reports about the site’s performance. Instead of Google Analytics, Matomo does not compromise data security and privacy, guaranteeing full data ownership and that none of it is ever sent to other services and third parties.

Since its launch in M2, the website has received **864 visits**, **2.773 page visits**, **543 users** and **3.5 actions per visit**, including page views, downloads, outlinks and internal site searches per visit (*Data Analytics from February 2022 – M2 until June 21st, 2022- M5*)

Figure 17. View of Matomo dashboard

4.2 Promotional material

EUT has been in charge of the creation of all visual material to support dissemination activities such as conferences, congresses, or project events. GuestXR project has created in April 2022 (M4) a set of communication materials such as an info sheet, a brochure, a roll-up, a poster layout and a general project presentation.

These materials serve as the project's business card and will be distributed as widely as possible, including the general public, conferences, workshops and other events, from the beginning of the project.

All materials are stored digitally in the project's internal repository and on the project's website for broader dissemination. Promotional materials will be regularly updated following the project's developments.

4.2.1 Infosheet

An A-4 info-sheet, based on the main objectives of the project, the technology, and its expected results, was produced as a promotional material and published on the project's website.

Figure 18. GuestXR info sheet

4.2.2 Rollup

A project rollup has been produced to be used when attending to dissemination events and/or to share through GuestXR's communication channel.

Figure 3: GuestXR rollup

4.2.3 Trifold

A trifold describing GuestXR project has been elaborated during the first months and shared to all consortium.

Figure 20. GuestXR trifold

4.2.4 Project general presentation

To support the communication of the GuestXR project, a PowerPoint presentation was prepared. Each partner can add new slides and complete the presentation according to their needs and to the event to be attended and/or audience.

The general presentation designed provides a general overview of the project, its main objectives, project phases, use cases, research beyond the state of the art, and information about The Guest.

Figure 21. View of GuestXR Power Point general presentation

4.2.5 Poster layout

A poster layout was designed to be used and adapted by all partners when need it. The document includes guidelines on how to structure the content and information along with the poster.

4.2.6 Audiovisual materials

On the other hand, to communicate the GuestXR project and its results several videos are planned. For now, 5 videos were produced, which have been published on the YouTube project channel:

[GuestXR application: adapting VR environment into 3D restaurant for a newspaper interview.](#) A video about the development of a 3D Virtual Reality restaurant environment for a Financial Times newspaper interview. **February 2022.**

[Interacting with virtual humanoids: from self-avatars to crowds](#). Video recording of a talk was given within a consortium meeting of the GuestXR project. **April 2022.**

Figure SEQ Figure * ARABIC 24. Screenshot of the video "Interacting with virtual humanoids: from self-avatars to crowds"

[GuestXR - Social Interaction in VR - Dr Sylvia Xueni Pan](#). Video recording of a talk to present how VR can improve the way we socially connect and communicate with each other in a face-to-face setting. **May 2022.**

Figure 25. Screenshot of the video "GuestXR - Social Interaction in VR - Dr. Sylvia Xueni Pan"

- Gaze associated with conversational attention
- Mutual awareness of gaze
- Appropriate flow of conversation
- Task performance superior to video
- Tracked gaze rated as superior to static gaze (and model based gaze)
- Eye gaze becomes a general social resource.
- Eye gaze leads to better detection of lying.

[Webinar - The Affordances and Problems of meeting in Virtual Reality](#). Video recording of the first webinar of the series of seminars "Striving for Social Harmony in XR". **May 2022.**

Figure 26. Screenshot of the video "Webinar - The Affordances and Problems of meeting in Virtual Reality"

[Webinar - Neuroscience of interpersonal interaction](#). Video recording of the second webinar of the series of seminars "Striving for Social Harmony in XR". **June 2022.**

Figure 27. Screenshot of the video "Webinar - Neuroscience of interpersonal interaction"

4.2.6.1 Planned audiovisual materials

Engaging audio-visual materials (e.g., videos) have been proposed to present the key aspects of the project. The videos produced within the project are published on the GuestXR website, and the YouTube channel and promoted on all project channels.

The proposed videos to be produced (to be confirmed) are:

- **Bimonthly consortium meeting lectures (M1-M48):** at every bimonthly meeting, a keynote speaker is invited to deliver a talk to all the consortium. The recordings of these videos are edited and published online for other interested stakeholders.
- **Webinars (M1-M48):** a series of webinars are being organised on project topics annually. Recordings are made available as videos through the YouTube channel and website.
- **Project video presentation (M12):** a video to present the project will be produced for non-specialised and specialised audiences to be used in dissemination events.
- **Case studies and experiments video (M1-M48):** videos explaining the case studies results and experiments carried out by research partners.
- **Project results video (M48):** final video to present the project results in audiovisual form.

4.3 Social media

Eurecat will manage GuestXR's social media accounts, and its contents described hereinafter. GuesXR project will count usage of a **Twitter Channel**, [@GuestXR](#), a **LinkedIn channel**, and a [YouTube channel](#).

On the other hand, **partners contribute to spreading the word on their corporate and personal Social Media channels**, including accounts on Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn or Instagram.

The project coordinator is responsible for notifying the European Commission about the possible content of interest to be published through its official social media channels and, whenever possible, will promote the use of social media complicities between GuestXR and its sister projects (@CarouselDancing, @SONICOMproject, @experience_FET, @Touchless_EU, etc.).

4.3.1 Twitter

The GuestXR Twitter account will be managed by EUT, with the support of project partners for its correct management.

The main objective of this account is to raise awareness on the potential impacts of GuestXR research and outputs, share news on VR, AR, and XR environments, and associated ethics, neuroscience, and other challenges for positive social interaction. Twitter will be also used to connect with EU institutions and related projects and initiatives.

Figure 4: GuestXR Twitter account

the account.

Relevant stakeholders and partners with a professional Twitter account will be followed by the GuestXR account to boost the visibility of

4.3.1.1 Account strategy

EUT creates a regular plan of content to be disseminated through the GuestXR Twitter account. All consortium partners can propose content (text, images, videos...) to be distributed in this channel and spread the word through their own social media channels by sharing and engaging with the content.

A Hootsuite account, a tool facilitating the publication of content and activity monitoring, has been created for scheduling tweets and shortening URLs. Comments and answers will be managed manually, to facilitate the removal of potential fake users or spam content.

4.3.1.2 Content strategy

When creating and publishing content about the project, EUT and the rest of the partners will consider the following recommendations to maximise the impact of the messages.

The strategy mixes marketing content, branding, and influence actions to maximise the project's impact and awareness.

Content strategy:

- **Disseminating project activities:** sharing information on project events, milestones, developments accomplished, and other dissemination activities organised by the project, including text and photos if possible.
- **Content curation:** sharing news on VR, AR, XR, and other immersive environments, ethics and neuroscience research applicable to VR, haptics, AI and Machine Learning, 3D audio, etc.
- **Disseminating audio-visual and promotional materials produced** (to make the project more accessible/understandable).
- **Sharing news and articles published on the website** to increase traffic.
- To increase the reach of the tweets, the frequent use of the following hashtags is proposed:
 - **Project:** #GuestXR #GuestXRproject #TheGuest #ResearchImpactEu #Horizon2020 #H2020
 - **VR, AR & related industries:** #VR, #AR, #XR, #VirtualReality, #AugmentedReality, #MixedReality, #ExtendedReality, #ImmersiveEnvironments, #3DAudio, #BinauralAudio, #ImmersiveAudio, #audiology, #haptics, #HapticsTechnology, #DeepLearning, #ReinforcementLearning, #RL, #MachineLearning, #ML, #AI, #ArtificialIntelligence, #Artificial_Intelligence, #SocialPhysiology #HumanBehaviour #ethics #neuroscience
 - **Other:** #tech #technology #innovation #metaverse #DigitalEU
- Project partners corporate and personal accounts (@Eurecat_news, @vbwks, @ReichmanUni, @Inria, @UniWarszawski, @gtec_bci, @MelSlater, @BodiesBig,

@RelevanceERCSyn, etc.) will be mentioned when publishing news about them to promote likes and retweets from partners.

- Accounts and content from projects funded under the same topic (@CarouselDancing, @SONICOMproject, @experience_FET, @Touchless_EU, etc.) will also be mentioned and retweeted.

Branding strategy:

- Twitter posts will be prepared to cover fairs, trade shows, congresses, and other events where GuestXR participates, using the official hashtag of the event (e.g., #IEEE, #ICIP2022, etc.).
- The official GuestXR Twitter account will be referenced in the partner's corporate accounts for a broader reach of the project

Influencer strategy:

- Accounts such as @EU_H2020 @EuScienceInnov @CORDIS_EU @EU_commission @EU_EISMEA, @DigitalEU will be regularly mentioned in tweets to get a bigger impact when project news or information about results is published.
- Influencers in the field of Extended Reality, Virtual Reality, Augmented Reality, and neuroscience, among other topics will be identified and mentioned in relevant posts.
- Stakeholder's accounts will be identified to promote follow-back and to increase the number of GuestXR followers.
- Media will be mentioned if they are publishing information about the project.

4.3.1.3 Analytics

A profile in Twitter Analytics has been activated to measure the Twitter KPIs (see Section 3.3 for more information) and other data about the account activity. Progress until the end of the project will be reported in the interim progress reports.

Figure 5: View of GuestXR analytics profile

4.3.2 LinkedIn

Figure 6: View of GuestXR LinkedIn account

LinkedIn is a platform for interaction among professionals to exchange experiences to improve their work placement. The portal allows the user to create interest groups around specific initiatives or projects, ask or answer questions, post or search for jobs, etc.

GuestXR partner EUT has created a LinkedIn page on M5, which allows having a corporate timeline where the project and connect with the industrial and academic community, as well as connect and engage with VR and AR stakeholders.

The publication pace in LinkedIn will be less frequent than on Twitter. Content will be based on project news, dissemination events, and reports/publications produced in the framework of the project or by trusted sources.

4.3.2.1 Account strategy

The LinkedIn account will be managed by EUT. Bimonthly content plans will be produced to ensure a regular publication pace. Contents will include:

- Audio-visual and digital promotional materials.
- Press releases produced
- News produced by project partners published on the GuestXR website.
- Specific information on the VR, AR, XR sector, and virtual environments that can be of interest to the industrial community
- The latest project-related research.
- Participation in key fairs and congresses on the project topics
- Promotion of webinars, stakeholder events, and other project activities.

All consortium partners can propose contents (text, images, videos...) to be distributed through this channel and can spread the word through their own corporate and personal channels by sharing the content published.

Publishing, as well as comments, answers, and private messages will be managed manually, to facilitate the removal of potential fake users or spam content. Hashtags will be used following the same guidelines defined for Twitter.

4.3.2.2 Analytics

Data on publications' impact will be retrieved from LinkedIn Analytics. Progress until the end of the project will be reported in the interim progress reports.

Figure 7: View of GuestXR LinkedIn Analytics

4.3.3 YouTube

The European Commission recommends the use of audio-visual resources to bring the results of the research projects closer to the general public.

A YouTube Channel has been created to allocate all videos produced during the project. All videos published are shared on the website and on the project's social media accounts for a broader impact. At M6, 6 videos have been published based on lectures given by keynotes in project consortium meetings or the recordings of the webinars organised during the project.

Figure 8: View of GuestXR YouTube channel

4.3.4 Partners channels

All partners help transmit GuestXR news and results through their personal and corporate social media accounts (Twitter, LinkedIn, Facebook, and Instagram), including press releases, news about events, promotional materials, and other content published on www.guestxr.eu or in the project Twitter account.

GuestXR's partner's impact on corporate social media channels will reach more than **77K users on Twitter**, more than **321K on LinkedIn**, more than **170K on Facebook** followers, **89K on YouTube**, and **75K on Instagram**.

Table 3: Partners Social Media channels

PARTNER	LinkedIn	Twitter	Facebook	Instagram
EUT	https://www.linkedin.com/company-beta/9355193/	@Eurecat_News	https://www.facebook.com/Eurecatorq/	N/A
VBW	https://www.linkedin.com/company/virtual-bodyworks/	@vbwrks	https://www.facebook.com/vbwrks/	https://www.instagram.com/vbwrks/
IDCH	https://www.linkedin.com/school/the-interdisciplinary-center-herzliya/	@ReichmanUni	https://www.facebook.com/ReichmanUniversity	https://www.instagram.com/reichmanuni/
UM	https://www.linkedin.com/school/fasos/	@BodiesBig @RelevanceERCSyn	https://www.facebook.com/maastrichtfasos	https://www.instagram.com/maastrichtuniversity
INRIA	https://www.linkedin.com/company/inria/	@Inria	https://www.facebook.com/Inria.fr	N/A
UW	https://www.linkedin.com/company/uniwersytet-warszawski/	@UniWarszawski	https://www.facebook.com/fanpageUW	https://www.instagram.com/uniwersytetwarszawski/
G.TEC	https://www.linkedin.com/company/gtec-medical-engineering	@gtec_bci	https://www.facebook.com/gtecmedicalengineering/	https://www.instagram.com/gtec.at/
UB	linkedin.com/in/mel-slater-491a07108	@MelSlater	https://www.facebook.com/melslater2	https://www.instagram.com/unibarcelona/

In addition, partners with Social Media presence will use their personal accounts to publish news about GuestXR developments.

Table 4: Personal accounts used to share GuestXR content

Name	Entity	Twitter handle	# Followers
Mel Slater	UB	@MelSlater	3582
Beatrice de Gelder	UM	@BodiesBig	1001
Anatole Lecuyer	Inria	@AnatoleLecuyer	464
Darian Meacham	UM	@PostEurope	1234
Dani Shanley	UM	@DaniShanley	368
Doron Friedman	IDCH	@Doronf	128

4.3.5 Guidelines for publishing about the project on social media

Partners are suggested to apply the following recommendations when communication about the project on social media:

- Use #GuestXR or #GuestXRproject hashtag
- Mention @GuestXR if you are using Twitter or tag the LinkedIn account GuestXR.
- Mention project partners to increase your reach
- Share links to project website/materials
- Communicate your role/task on the project

Partners can also use the guidelines prepared for the project's Twitter when publishing about the project in social media.

4.4 Media relations

Press releases will be written and sent to relevant media at regular intervals, focusing on the release of research results, milestones, meetings, attendance to or organisation of events etc., and connected with newsworthy initiatives when possible.

All press releases will be distributed among partners in English for providing feedback (where appropriate), giving them the opportunity to adapt the documents in their corporate language and to circulate them among their regional media contacts.

Apart from consortium press releases, country-focused press releases or press releases oriented to specific stakeholder groups or stakeholders may be elaborated by partners, after informing the Project Coordinator and Communication Leader (EUT). Also, GuestXR partners will consider interview offerings and a press conference at the end of the project to showcase the main project results to the media.

In the framework of the project, a database with the contact details of partners' communication officers has been created, to facilitate the review of the media materials, coordinate the sending of the press releases and increase the project's impact across European media outlets.

A database with specialised media covering VR, AR, and XR will be created, primarily with outlets located in the partners' countries.

4.4.1 Outlets of interest

During the project a minimum of 20 publications in generalist media outlets and 10 articles in key specialized magazines, such as the listed in table 5 are planned. The schedule, partner responsible, and magazine selection, as well as the tracking media appearances, will be discussed in partners meetings.

The objective is for a wide range of readers to reach the project topics involved in academia, as well as industry. An initial list of European / Global specialised media outlets identified as relevant to promote GuestXR outputs include:

Table 5: List of identified specialised outlets

Outlet name	Website	Language
Virtual Reality World Tech Magazine	https://vrworldtech.com	English
The Virtual Report	https://www.thevirtualreport.biz	English
AR – VR Magazine	https://arvmagazine.com	English
Mixed	https://mixed-news.com	English

VR 360	https://www.virtualreality-news.net/	English
XR Today	https://www.xrtoday.com	English
Xataka	https://www.xataka.com	Spanish
Real o Virtual	https://www.realovirtual.com/	Spanish

4.4.2 Press release production

Press releases will be following WP work and main deliverables and milestones. At M6 a first press release on project objectives and expected impacts has been produced.

New machine learning agent addresses conflicts and unlocks interaction in extended reality environments such as the metaverse

- The European project GuestXR is to examine individual and group behaviour in extended reality environments by drawing on existing theoretical models from the neuroscience and social psychology standpoint.
- The innovation seeks to help avert conflicts and cyberbullying in digital interaction environments, make it easier for people with communication problems to get involved, detect antisocial behaviour and tackle other similar issues.
- The solution is to be tested in contexts in which discussion topics such as climate change might generate heated debate.

Barcelona, xx of xx 2022. The European project GuestXR is to develop an immersive virtual social space anchored in extended reality. It will feature a machine learning agent designed to unlock interactions between participants and help them achieve their goals while it additionally supports addressing conflicts in virtual environments such as the metaverse.

A machine learning system called 'The Guest' is to be devised as an agent that can examine participants' individual and group behaviour by drawing on existing theoretical models from the neuroscience and social psychology standpoint. Deep Reinforcement Learning will also give it the ability to learn over time and become more effective in terms of social interaction, learning from both simulations and real human meetings.

"Every gathering of people in virtual and augmented reality has a purpose – either an explicit one, such as to reach an agreement on a topic of discussion, or an implicit one such as enjoyment. The fundamental idea of 'the Guest' is to help the group of people realise this purpose. This involves exciting research with a strong interdisciplinary component, breaking new ground, and hopefully contributing to the success of social Virtual and Augmented Reality," says Mel Slater, GuestXR scientific leader from the University of Barcelona.

To modulate this social interaction, 'The Guest' will be able to perform a range of multisensory actions "using, for instance, visual or auditory features to create particular states of mind and stimulate a relaxed environment when it identifies a conflict," says Aurora Sesé, GuestXR project coordinator at the Eurecat technology centre.

This project "is designed to help deliver solutions to existing challenges in online environments of social interaction like cyberbullying, for which there is no specific European legislation as yet," she adds.

The intervention of the machine learning system will be initially tested in conflict resolution situations, in interactions involving hearing impaired participants or in contexts that trigger debate such as climate change.

Finally, there will be two open calls to include other innovative use cases to check the system's effectiveness: one addressed to the general society (including companies, associations, etc.) and the other one specifically addressed to people from the arts world.

The GuestXR technology will be developed under the "Ethics by Design" approach. This entails considering any potential ethical issues which may come up when using Artificial Intelligence such as respect for human autonomy, prevention of harm, fairness and explicability.

The GuestXR consortium is coordinated by the Eurecat technology centre together with the University of Barcelona and it is made up of eight organisations from six countries featuring a multidisciplinary team with backgrounds in extended reality, machine learning, artificial intelligence, social psychology, the neuroscience of emotions, multisensory integration, research ethics and technology transfer.

Alongside [Eurecat](#), four universities (the [University of Maastricht](#), the [University of Warsaw](#), the [University of Barcelona](#) and the [Reichman University](#)), a research institute ([Inria](#)) and two businesses ([Virtual Bodyworks](#) and [a.tec medical engineering GMBH](#)) are also taking part in the project.

Figure 33: First press release of the project: <https://guestxr.eu/new-machine-learning-agent-addresses-conflicts-and-unlocks-interaction-in-extended-reality-environments-such-as-the-metaverse/>

Based on this press release partners EUT, UB and INRIA produced regional versions, published on their website and distributed to their media contacts:

Eurecat Àmbits de Coneixement Sectors Serveis Projectes Actualitat Contacte [in](#) [y](#) [t](#) [w](#) [f](#) [Català](#) [Q](#)

Un agent d'aprenentatge automàtic abordarà conflictes i facilitarà la interacció en entorns de realitat estesa com el metavers
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Un agent d'aprenentatge automàtic abordarà conflictes i facilitarà la interacció en entorns de realitat estesa com el metavers

Un agent d'aprenentatge automàtic abordarà conflictes i facilitarà la interacció en entorns de realitat estesa com el metavers

El centre tecnològic Eurecat lidera el projecte europeu GuestXR, que desenvoluparà un agent d'aprenentatge automàtic dissenyat per facilitar les interaccions entre els participants en entorns de realitat virtual i augmentada, com el metavers, i per ajudar-los a assolir els seus objectius, alhora que permetrà abordar situacions de conflicte.

Amb aquesta finalitat, es dissenyarà un sistema d'aprenentatge automàtic anomenat el 'convivat' ('Guest'), que funcionarà com un agent capaç d'examinar el comportament individual i grupal dels participants basant-se en models existents des del punt de vista de la neurociència i de la psicologia social. A més, el *Deep Reinforcement Learning* també donarà al 'convivat' la capacitat d'aprendre amb el temps i ser més eficaç pel que fa a la interacció social, aprenent tant de simulacions com de reunions reals entre persones.

En aquesta línia, l'agent "podrà intervenir en la conversa de maneres diverses com, per exemple, aportant experiències multisensorials a través de música o de canvis en l'espai, entre d'altres", destaca el director de Tecnologies Audiovisuais d'Eurecat, Adan Garriga.

"Cada reunió de persones en la realitat virtual i augmentada té un propòsit, ja sigui explícit, com arribar a un acord sobre un tema de discussió, o implícit, com ara el gaudi. La idea fonamental del 'convivat' és ajudar el grup de persones a realitzar aquest propòsit. Això implica una investigació apassionant amb un fort component interdisciplinari, obre nous camins i, amb sort, contribueix a l'èxit de la realitat virtual i augmentada social", diu el coordinador científic del projecte GuestXR de la Universitat de Barcelona, Mel Slater, membre de l'Institut de Neurociències de la UB (NeuroUB).

Per modular aquesta interacció social, el 'convivat' podrà dur a terme una sèrie d'accions multisensorials "utilitzant, per exemple, característiques visuals o auditives per crear estats mentals particulars i estimular un entorn relaxat quan identifiqui un conflicte", destaca l'investigador de Tecnologies Audiovisuais d'Eurecat Umut Sayin.

Aquest projecte "està dissenyat per ajudar a oferir solucions als reptes existents en entorns en línia d'interacció social com el ciberassetjament, per al qual encara no hi ha una legislació europea específica", explica la coordinadora del projecte GuestXR d'Eurecat, Aurora Sesé.

La intervenció del sistema d'aprenentatge automàtic es provarà inicialment en situacions de resolució de conflictes, en interaccions amb participants amb dificultats auditives i en contextos que desencadenen debats polaritzats com el canvi climàtic.

Finalment, hi haurà dues convocatòries obertes per incloure altres casos d'ús innovadors per comprovar l'eficàcia del sistema, una de les quals estarà adreçada a la societat en general, incloses empreses i associacions, entre d'altres, i l'altra específicament adreçada a persones del món de les arts.

La tecnologia GuestXR es desenvoluparà sota l'enfocament "Ethics by design". Això implica considerar els possibles problemes ètics que puguin sorgir quan s'utilitza la intel·ligència artificial, com ara el respecte a l'autonomia humana, la prevenció de danys, l'equitat i l'explicabilitat.

El consorci GuestXR està liderat pel centre tecnològic Eurecat juntament amb la Universitat de Barcelona i està format per vuit organitzacions de sis països amb un equip multidisciplinari amb formació en realitat estesa, aprenentatge automàtic, intel·ligència artificial, psicologia social, neurociència de les emocions, integració multisensorial, ètica de la recerca i transferència de tecnologia.

Juntament amb Eurecat, també hi participen quatre universitats (la Universitat de Maastricht, la Universitat de Varsòvia, la Universitat de Barcelona i la Universitat Reichman), un institut de recerca (Inria) i dues empreses (Virtual Bodyworks i g.tec medical engineering GMBH).

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Figure 9: Catalan press release produced by Eurecat - <https://eurecat.org/un-agent-daprenentatge-automat-ic-abordara-conflictes-i-facilitara-la-interaccio-en-entorns-de-realitat-estesa-com-el-metavers/>

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Un agente de aprendizaje automático abordará conflictos y facilitará la interacción en entornos de realidad extendida como el metaverso

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Un agente de aprendizaje automático abordará conflictos y facilitará la interacción en entornos de realidad extendida como el metaverso

El centro tecnológico Eurecat lidera el proyecto europeo GuestXR, que desarrollará un agente de aprendizaje automático diseñado para facilitar las interacciones entre los participantes en entornos de realidad virtual y aumentada, como el metaverso, y para ayudarlos a alcanzar sus objetivos, a la vez que permitirá abordar situaciones de conflicto.

Con este fin, se diseñará un sistema de aprendizaje automático llamado el 'invitado' ('Guest'), que funcionará como un agente capaz de examinar el comportamiento individual y grupal de los participantes en base a modelos existentes desde el punto de vista de la neurociencia y de la psicología social. Además, el Deep Reinforcement Learning también dará al 'invitado' la capacidad de aprender con el tiempo y ser más eficaz en cuanto a la interacción social, aprendiendo tanto de simulaciones como de reuniones reales entre personas.

En esta línea, el agente "podrá intervenir en la conversación de formas diversas como, por ejemplo, aportando experiencias multisensoriales a través de música o de cambios en el espacio, entre otros", destaca el director de Tecnologías Audiovisuales de Eurecat, Adan Garriga.

"Cada reunión de personas en la realidad virtual y aumentada tiene un propósito, ya sea explícito, como llegar a un acuerdo sobre un tema de discusión, o implícito, como el disfrute. La idea fundamental del 'invitado' es ayudar al grupo de personas a realizar este propósito. Esto implica una investigación apasionante con un fuerte componente interdisciplinario, abre nuevos caminos y, con suerte, contribuye al éxito de la realidad virtual y aumentada social", dice el coordinador científico del proyecto GuestXR de la Universitat de Barcelona, Mel Slater, miembro del Instituto de Neurociencias de la UB (NeuroUB).

Para modular esta interacción social, el 'invitado' podrá llevar a cabo una serie de acciones multisensoriales "utilizando, por ejemplo, características visuales o auditivas para crear estados mentales particulares y estimular un entorno relajado cuando identifique un conflicto", destaca el investigador de Tecnologías Audiovisuales de Eurecat Umut Sayin.

Este proyecto "está diseñado para ayudar a ofrecer soluciones a los retos existentes en entornos online de interacción social como el ciberacoso, para el que todavía no existe una legislación europea específica", explica la coordinadora del proyecto GuestXR de Eurecat, Aurora Sesé.

La intervención del sistema de aprendizaje automático se probará inicialmente en situaciones de resolución de conflictos, en interacciones con participantes con dificultades auditivas y en contextos que desencadenan debates polarizados como el cambio climático.

Por último, habrá dos convocatorias abiertas para incluir otros casos de uso innovadores para comprobar la eficacia del sistema, una de las cuales estará dirigida a la sociedad en general, incluidas empresas y asociaciones, entre otras, y otra específicamente dirigida a personas del mundo de las artes.

La tecnología GuestXR se desarrollará bajo el enfoque "Ethics by design". Esto implica considerar los posibles problemas éticos que puedan surgir cuando se utiliza la inteligencia artificial, como el respeto a la autonomía humana, la prevención de daños, la equidad y la explicabilidad.

El consorcio GuestXR está liderado por el centro tecnológico Eurecat junto con la Universitat de Barcelona y está formado por ocho organizaciones de seis países con un equipo multidisciplinar con formación en realidad extendida, aprendizaje automático, inteligencia artificial, psicología social, neurociencia de las emociones, integración multisensorial, ética de la investigación y transferencia de tecnología.

Junto con Eurecat, también participan cuatro universidades (la Universidad de Maastricht, la Universidad de Varsovia, la Universitat de Barcelona y la Universidad Reichman), un instituto de investigación (Inria) y dos empresas (Virtual Bodyworks y g.tec medical engineering GmbH).

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Figure 10: Spanish press release produced by EUT - <https://eurecat.org/es/un-agente-de-aprendizaje-automatico-abordara-conflictos-y-facilitara-la-interaccion-en-entornos-de-realidad-extendida-como-el-metaverso/>

Noticias

Inicio > Noticias > GuestXR: un agente de aprendizaje automático para mejorar la gestión de conflictos...

GuestXR: un agente de aprendizaje automático para mejorar la gestión de conflictos en entornos virtuales

Con esta innovación se pretende ayudar a gestionar conflictos y situaciones de ciberacoso en entornos de realidad virtual y aumentada.

El profesor Mel Slater, de la Facultad de Psicología y el Instituto de Neurociencias de la UB (NeuroUB).

16/05/2022

Recerca

Desarrollar un agente de aprendizaje automático para facilitar las interacciones entre los participantes en entornos de realidad virtual y aumentada —como el metaverso— con el fin de ayudarles a alcanzar sus objetivos y abordar situaciones de conflicto: esta es la intención principal del proyecto europeo «A machine learning agent for social harmony in extended reality» (GuestXR), cuyo coordinador científico es el profesor Mel Slater, de la Facultad de Psicología y el Instituto de Neurociencias de la UB (NeuroUB).

En el marco del proyecto GuestXR, que está coordinado por el centro tecnológico Eurecat, se diseñará un sistema de aprendizaje automático llamado *el invitado* (*the guest*), que funcionará como un agente capaz de examinar el comportamiento individual y grupal de los participantes en función de los modelos existentes en el contexto de la neurociencia y la psicología social. Además, el aprendizaje profundo por refuerzo (*deep reinforcement learning*) también dará al invitado la capacidad de aprender con el tiempo —tanto de simulaciones como de reuniones reales— y ser más eficaz en las interacciones sociales. En esta línea, el agente «podrá intervenir en la conversación de formas diversas, como por ejemplo aportando experiencias multisensoriales a través de música o de cambios en el espacio, entre otras», destaca el director de la Unidad de Tecnologías Audiovisuales de Eurecat, Adan Garriga.

«Cada reunión de personas en la realidad virtual y aumentada tiene un propósito, ya sea explícito (por ejemplo, llegar a un acuerdo sobre un tema de discusión) o implícito (como el disfrute). La idea fundamental del invitado es ayudar al grupo de personas a realizar ese propósito. Eso implica una investigación apasionante, con un fuerte componente interdisciplinario, que abre nuevos caminos y, con suerte, contribuye al éxito social de la realidad virtual y aumentada», explica el profesor Mel Slater.

Para modular la interacción social, el invitado podrá llevar a cabo una serie de acciones multisensoriales «mediante, por ejemplo, elementos visuales o auditivos para crear estados mentales particulares y estimular un entorno

relajado cuando identifique un conflicto», destaca Umut Sayin, investigador de la Unidad de Tecnologías Audiovisuales de Eurecat.

Este proyecto «está diseñado para ayudar a ofrecer soluciones a los retos existentes en entornos de interacción social en línea, como el ciberacoso, para el que todavía no existe una legislación europea específica», explica la coordinadora del proyecto GuestXR por parte de Eurecat, Aurora Sesé.

La intervención del sistema de aprendizaje automático se probará inicialmente en situaciones de resolución de conflictos, interacciones con participantes con dificultades auditivas y contextos que desencadenan debates polarizados, como el del cambio climático.

Con el fin de comprobar la eficacia del sistema, está previsto que se abran dos convocatorias para incluir otros casos de uso innovadores. Una de ellas se dirigirá a la sociedad en general —incluidas empresas y asociaciones, entre otras entidades—, mientras que la otra tendrá como objetivo el colectivo del mundo de las artes.

La tecnología GuestXR se desarrollará bajo el enfoque del diseño ético (*ethics by design*), que implica considerar los posibles problemas éticos derivados del uso de la inteligencia artificial relativos a aspectos como la autonomía humana, la prevención de daños o la equidad.

El consorcio GuestXR, coordinado por la UB y el centro tecnológico Eurecat, está integrado por ocho organizaciones de seis países con equipos multidisciplinares que investigan en los ámbitos de la realidad extendida, el aprendizaje automático, la inteligencia artificial, la psicología social, la neurociencia de las emociones, la integración multisensorial, la ética de la investigación y la transferencia de tecnología. También colaboran en él la Universidad de Maastricht (Países Bajos), la Universidad de Varsovia (Polonia) y la Universidad Reichman (Israel), así como el Instituto Nacional de Investigación en Ciencias y Tecnologías Digitales (INRIA) de Francia y las empresas Virtual Bodyworks y g.tec medical engineering GmbH.

Compártelo en: Más |

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Figure 11: GuestXR UB press release

https://www.ub.edu/web/ub/es/menu_eines/noticies/2022/05/030.html?

Inria

Europe

GuestXR, a virtual agent to assist interactions in an immersive space

Date: 25 Apr. 2022

Home > News and events > GuestXR, a virtual agent to assist interactions in an immersive space

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GuestXR, a virtual agent to assist interactions in an immersive space

Within the framework of the European Research Area (ERA), the Institute is strengthening its collaboration with its European partners. It relies on the programmes and partnerships organised by the European Commission (in particular within the framework of Horizon Europe and Digital Europe) but also, in a stronger dynamic of integration, develops actions aiming to jointly carry out initiatives and shared roadmaps at the European level.

GuestXR, a virtual agent to assist interactions in an immersive space

- What are the objectif of the project ?
- What type of European funding does the project receive?
- Who are the European partners of the project?

Discover European project FetProactive GuestXR coordinated by Eurecat and supported by Anatole Lecuyer, head of project team Hybrid.

Project team Hybrid: The research activity of Hybrid team belongs to the field of Virtual Reality and 3D interaction with Virtual Environments. Project team's objective is to invent novel 3D interactive techniques with virtual environments exploiting both the body and brain of the user. Applications of their research program are for industry (virtual prototyping), medicine (surgical simulation, rehabilitation and reeducation), design (architectural mock-up), art or videogames and entertainment. Hybrid was created in January 2013. Learn more about Hybrid

Inria

GuestXR, a virtual agent to assist interactions in an immersive space

The EU-funded GuestXR project intends to develop a socially interactive multisensory platform system that uses extended reality – virtual and augmented – as a vehicle to connect people for immersive, synchronous face to face interaction with positive social results.

@guestxr.eu

What are the objectives of the project ?

A machine learning agent called "The Guest" will be created to analyze the individual and social behavior of participants based on existing theoretical models from the perspective of neuroscience and social psychology.

The Guest will be trained to facilitate different types of social interaction, including situations that may involve conflict, with participants with hearing impairments, or involving a change in attitude towards controversial topics.

GuestXR's innovations are therefore aimed at reducing conflict and cyberbullying in virtual environments, facilitating the participation of people with communication problems, and detecting anti-social behavior for example

What type of European funding does the project receive?

"For this very ambitious and highly multi-disciplinary scientific and technological project, we logically targeted European funding, under the Horizon 2020 FETPROACT-2020-2 program."

« Being part of a European project means being able to propose a very rich consortium with partners with varied and very complementary expertise »

Who are the European partners of the project?

In addition to Inria, the consortium brings together: [Eurecat](#) (Spain), [Virtual Body Works](#) (Spain), [IDCH](#) (Israel), [Maastricht University](#) (Netherlands), [g.tec](#) (Austria), [Universitat de Barcelona](#) (Spain), [Reichmann University](#) (Israel), [Uniwersytet Warszawski](#) (Poland).

Figure 12: Adaptation of the press release published on INRIA website

During the project 4 press releases will be produced annually. A preliminary press release calendar has been produced:

Table 6: Preliminary press release calendar

GuestXR press release plan		Partners leading
M1	1 st press release of the project (PUBLISHED)	EUT, distributed in partners regions
M18	Open Call Launch	EUT, distributed in partners regions
M24	Open call results – selected application	EUT, distributed in partners regions
MX	Climate change use case	UW
MX	Conflict resolution use case	UB
MX	Hearing loss use case	IDCH
MX	Open call experiment	EUT, distributed in partners regions
M48	Final results	EUT, all partners

4.4.3 Media impacts

The press release produced had an important impact on online and print media. As a result, GuestXR project has been featured in **20 media outlets at a regional, national, and international level**, including 5 sectorial outlets (e.g. TechXPlore, Intelligence Artificiel) and 15 articles in generalist outlets, highlighting an article in La Vanguardia, one of Spain's major newspapers with a daily audience of over 2M readers online. Articles have been published in several languages, including Catalan, Spanish, English, French and Russian.

Table 7: List of media articles featuring GuestXR

Date	Media	Title	Type	Language	Link
5/11/2022	La Vanguardia	Sistema de aprendizaje automático ayudará a gestionar conflictos y ciberacoso	Online	Spanish	Link
5/11/2022	SumIndustria	El centro tecnológico Eurecat está presente a partir de hoy en el Integrated Systems Europe (ISE),	Online	Spanish	Link
5/12/2022	viaempresa.cat	El proyecto GuestXR gestionará conflictos y situaciones de ciberacoso	Online	Spanish	Link
5/12/2022	espai.media	Eurecat dissenya un projecte per interactuar amb seny en entorns de realitat virtual	Online	Catalan	Link
5/16/2022	Innovation Origins	Machine learning tool improves conflict management in the metaverse	Online	English	Link
5/16/2022	TechXplore	Researchers plan to develop a machine learning agent for improving conflict management in virtual environments	Online	English	Link
5/16/2022	Mtech News	GuestXR: Machine learning agent for improving	Online	English	Link

5/16/2022	Mirage News	GuestXR: machine learning agent for improving conflict management in virtual environments	Online	English	Link
5/16/2022	USA News	GuestXR: Machine learning agent for improving	Online	English	Link
5/16/2022	Tech Tribune	Un outil d'apprentissage automatique améliore la gestion des conflits dans le métaverse	Online	French	Link
5/16/2022	MyScience	GuestXR: machine learning agent for improving conflict management in virtual environments	Online	English	Link
5/17/2022	Alpha Galileo	GuestXR: un agente de aprendizaje automático para mejorar la gestión de conflictos en entornos virtuales	Online	Spanish	Link
5/17/2022	Blockchain 24	Инструмент машинного обучения улучшает управление конфликтами в метавселенной	Online	Russian	Link
5/17/2022	Intelligence Artificielle	Machine learning : améliorer la gestion des conflits dans le metaverse	Online	French	Link
5/18/2022	Media Automate	GuestXR: Machine studying agent for enhancing	Online	English	Link
5/18/2022	Ma4t	GuestXR: Machine Learning Agent for Improvement	Online	English	Link
17/05/2022	EurekAlert!	GuestXR: Machine learning agent for improving conflict management in virtual environments	Online	English	Link
18/05/2022	NFT Time	GuestXR: Machine learning agent for improving	Online	English	Link
18/05/2022	AGADIR-GROUP	GuestXR: Enhanced for machine learning agent	Online	English	Link
18/05/2022	Paywise	GuestXR: Machine Learning Agent for Improvement	Online	English	Link

4.5 Community of interest / newsletter

Direct communication be established through direct mailing to increase the impact of our communication and dissemination activities. In that regard, a community of interest around the project has been created.

The database of subscribers will be built during the whole project and will be gained progressively via a sign-up form published on the website homepage and promoted via social media channels, as well as partners' channels.

News and updated and specific information about the project will be distributed periodically via mailing campaigns to ensure that all subscribers to our community are regularly informed about our latest achievements.

Subscribers can register through a sign-up form compliant with GDPR, linking to the project's privacy policy and informing the user about their right to cancel the subscription at any time. The registration page has been shared broadly throughout GuestXR social media channels and is available on the website.

Figure 38: Banner used on Social Media to promote the newsletter

Mailchimp will be used as the email platform to be used for sending the updated and specific information. Subscriptions and Desubscriptions will be managed automatically via Mailchimp. Data collected through the sign-up form will be used for the exclusive purpose of sending subscribers information related to the project and will never be passed to third-party companies unless there is a legal obligation to do so.

Newsletter analytics, such as the open rate or click-through rate, are extracted through Mailchimp platform. Statistics have been checked 3 days after sending the newsletter and have been analysed in order to see which articles worked best so we are able to improve the newsletter impact in the following issues.

During the project, four newsletters will be produced (1 annually):

Table 8: Newsletter calendar

GuestXR Newsletters	Month
1 st newsletter	M11
2 nd newsletter	M23
3 rd newsletter	M35
4 th newsletter	M48

4.6 Public engagement activities

4.6.1 Series of webinars

GuestXR launched at the beginning of May (M5) a series of five webinars named “**Striving for Social Harmony in XR**”, where GuestXR partners deliver talks on topics related to the project.

These seminars are being recorded, and uploaded to our dedicated page through our YouTube channel. The visual support used by the speakers is also uploaded on the GuestXR website in PDF format.

GUESTXR www.guestxr.eu

Frontiers in Virtual Reality Online Seminar Series

- 25/05 - The affordances and problems of meeting in virtual reality
- 8/06 - Neuroscience of Interpersonal Interaction
- 22/06 - Getting Real about ethics in virtual environments
- 29/06 - Social modeling
- 06/07 - Deep learning for virtual humans in XR: beyond photorealism

Figure 40. GuestXR series of webinars "Striving for Social Harmony in GuestXR"

A series of webinars will be organised yearly between April and June by GuestXR partners to transmit the research to the academic and industry audience. In total 16 webinars will be organised during the project.

4.6.2 Interactive multistakeholder events: local events

For maximising the reach of project dissemination, 4 interactive multistakeholder local events are planned every year. These events will be organised by one of the partners and participated by other members of the consortium.

As of now, the Advanced Reality Lab – Reichman University (IDCH) has organised a **Symposium named "XR for the people"**, celebrated on June 2022 (M6). The event was participated by the University of Maastricht and the University of Barcelona.

For every event, a specific page will be created on the website with all the information needed in order to join it.

Symposium: XR for the people

Science, technology, applications, and implications

Date: June 13th, 2022

Time: 12:30h – 19:00h GMT+3

Venue: Reichman University, Chais Auditorium (CL05), Arazi-Ofer building

Address: HaUniversita 8 8, Herzliya, 4610101, Israel

Figure 41. View of a specific page for a local multistakeholder event

5. Planning calendar

Communication activities GuestXR	M6	M7	M8	M9	M10	M11	M12	M13	M14	M15	M16	M17
	jun-22	jul-22	aug-22	sep-22	oct-22	nov- 22	dec-22	jan-23	feb-23	mar-23	apr-23	may-23
Update Twitter Account	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Website Update	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Newsletter promotion	X	X	X	X	X							
Videos webinar series	X	X										
Stakeholder local events				X	X	X	X					
1 st newsletter						X						
Project dissemination video							X					
D6.3 Dissemination Plan							X					
Local stakeholders' events					X	X	X					
Videos consortium lectures				X			X		X		X	
2 nd year webinar series										X	X	X
Videos webinar series 2 nd yr										X	X	X
Dissemination video							X					
	M18	M19	M20	M21	M22	M23	M24	M25	M26	M27	M28	M29
	jun-23	jul-23	aug-23	sep-23	oct-23	nov-23	dec-23	jan-24	feb-24	mar-24	apr-24	may-24
Update Twitter Account	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Website Update	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Videos consortium lectures	X			X		X		X		X		
Press release – Open Call launch	X											
2 nd year local stakeholder events				X	X	X						

2 nd newsletter							X						
Press release – Open Call results								X					
3 rd year webinar series											X	X	X
Videos webinar series 3 rd yr											X	X	X
Videos on case studies and experiments							X	X	X	X	X	X	X
	M30	M31	M32	M33	M34	M35	M36	M37	M38	M39	M40	M41	
	jun-24	jul-24	aug-24	sep-24	oct-24	nov-24	dec-24	jan-25	feb-25	mar-25	apr-25	may-25	
Update Twitter Account	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Website Update	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Videos on case studies and experiments	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Press releases – Case studies results	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Videos consortium lectures	X			X		X		X		X			
3 rd year local stakeholder events				X	X	X							
3 rd newsletter						X							
4 th year webinar series											X	X	X
Videos webinar series 4 th yr											X	X	X
	M42	M43	M44	M45	M46	M47	M48						
	jun-25	jul-25	aug-25	sep-25	oct-25	nov-25	dec-25						
Update Twitter Account	X	X	X	X	X	X	X						
Website Update	X	X	X	X	X	X	X						
Videos on case studies and experiments	X	X	X	X	X	X	X						
Videos consortium lectures	X			X		X							

4th Newsletter						X							
4th year stakeholder events				X	X	X							
Final video							X						
Final press releases							X						
Final event							X						

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